

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY CLASSES BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODS

Dilorom Xudayqulovna Alimova

Teacher of the Faculty of Pedagogy of Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7876527>

***Abstract.** This article discusses about the content and essence of interactive techniques that serve students to obtain more meaningful knowledge and help to organize teachers' lessons in an interesting way, and the stages of their application in primary education lessons.*

***Keywords:** Primary education, method, interactive, interactive method, interactive learning, lesson, organization, stage, method, boomerang, Alphabet method.*

True education is to prepare a person for humanity

N.I.Pirogov

Solving the complex tasks of educating young people depends on the professional skills, talent, experience and culture of teachers, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, and the mutual activity of students.

Every pedagogue should always take into account and remember that the lesson is the main form of the educational process. In the course of the lesson, attention is paid to educating a well-rounded person. One of the main goals of education is to train and teach students how to learn by activating them during the lesson.

Teaching an interactive method to the student in the course of the lesson has a specific educational purpose. That is the most important importance of interactive methods. The purpose of education is formed and developed in accordance with the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate.

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, while the use of modern technologies teaches them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis, even to draw final conclusions themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for personal development, formation, learning and upbringing, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

That's why I use a new method or some constructive exercises in each of my lessons to increase the effectiveness of our lessons and encourage our students to actively participate.

I try to activate my students by introducing something new in my lessons. Now let me introduce the educational game known as "**Ladder**" that I used in my lesson. I think it is appropriate to use this educational game in the lessons of repeating the topics. Because the given tasks are given based on the topics covered.

According to the group, handouts are prepared, and from the last desk to the front desk, one by one tasks are solved and passed to the front desks. After reaching the first table, the competition condition is completed and the task is evaluated according to the answers.

For example, it can be as follows.

Students should write one answer in each cell of the table. Table cells are placed depending on the number of students and can give the following answers.

<u>Xorazmiy, Abu Ja'far (Abu Abdulloh) Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy</u>	<u>783-yil Xivada tug'ilgan</u>
<u>— xorazmlik matematik</u>	<u>astronom, geograf, fan tarixidagi ilk qomusiy olimlardan.</u>

<u>Abu Rayhon Muhammad ibn Ahmad Al-Beruniy</u>	<u>Islom davrining oltin zabardast Xorazmlik qomusiy allomalaridan biri.</u>
<u>Al-Beruniy nomi forscha „birun“ („chet“ degan ma'noni anglatadi) so'zidan olingan bo'lib,</u>	<u>u Afrig'iy Xorazmshohlar poytaxti Kat shahrining chekka tumanida tug'ilgan</u>

We can continue this educational game by putting the name of a section or the name of a subject instead of the great people in the first row. The information that the student knows about this topic is included in the given table, and at the end they are summarized.

Such interactive games are of great help to make the lesson interesting, to make teachers and students work on themselves and to increase the quality of education, as well as to increase the level of knowledge of students and to remember what they have memorized.

In conclusion, we can say that it is the demand of the day to try to move to the type aimed at the comprehensive development of human thinking, the practical application of the knowledge acquired by students, and the formation of practical skills and qualifications. All subjects taught in primary education ensure the effectiveness of students' acquisition of knowledge, skills and

abilities at the next stages of education. From this point of view, organizing the educational process using interactive methods is one of the urgent pedagogical problems. Only if this is achieved, the task of educating the young generation, which is the future of our country, can be solved rationally. The correct choice of educational methods and their appropriate use will help to ensure the effectiveness of education.

REFERENCES

1. O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 29-apreldagi “Xalq ta`limi tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to`g`risida”gi PF-5712-sonli farmoni
2. O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga murojaatnomasi
3. A.Musurmanova va boshqalar. Umumiy pedagogika – Toshkent. Innovatsiya – Ziyo.2020.-
4. O`. Q. Tolipov va M. Usmonboyeva .Pedagogik texnologiyalarning tatbiqiy asoslari – Toshkent.Fan. 2006.
5. R. Ishmuhammedov “O`quv jarayonida interfaol uslublar va pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo`llash uslubiyati”, Toshkent, RBIMM-2008 yil.